

A facile one pot synthesis of novel N_1 -(2-nitrophenyl sulphenyl substituted) pyrrolidino[2,1-*c*][1,4]-benzodiazepine, thiazolidino[3,2-*c*][1,4]-benzodiazepine and thiazolidino[4,3-*c*][1,4]-benzodiazepine from the corresponding N-substituted isatoic anhydride

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Abstract : A facile one pot synthesis of N_1 -(2-nitrophenyl sulphenyl substituted) pyrrolidino[2,1-*c*][1,4]-benzodiazepine (6), 4'-hydroxypyrrolidino[2,1-*c*][1,4]-benzodiazepine (7), thiazolidino[3,2-*c*][1,4]-benzodiazepine (8) and thiazolidino[4,3-*c*][1,4]-benzodiazepine (9) from the reaction of N_1 -(2-nitrophenyl sulphenyl) isatoic anhydride (1) with L-proline (2), 4-hydroxy-L-proline (3), thiazolidine-2-carboxylic acid (4) and thiazolidine-3-carboxylic acid (5) respectively has been described. The formation of 6, 7, 8 and 9 from 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively is believed to take place through the intermediate N-(2-nitrophenyl sulphenyl)-iminoketene (10).

Keywords : N_1 -Substituted-[1,4]-benzodiazepines, pyrrolidino- and thiazolidino-[1,4]-benzodiazepines, N-(2-nitrophenyl sulphenyl)isatoic anhydride.

Introduction

Ubiquitous presence of 1,4-benzodiazepines in chemical literature is undoubtedly a consequence of the multifarious biological responses which they elicit in combating a variety of body ailments. The use of this class of compounds is not merely confined to the management of anxiety of stress related conditions or their use as anti-neoplastic agents, but their additional novel applications have been continuously emerging¹⁻⁴. The recent demonstrations that these compounds can serve as potential agents in the control and treatment of AIDS has stimulated further interest in these compounds from yet another perspective⁵⁻⁷.

A systematic exploration of psychopharmacological properties of 1,4-benzodiazepines suggests that presence of a chloro (or nitro) group at C₇, a pyrrole ring at face 'c', a heterocyclic residue at face 'a' or face 'g' (involving N₁) was of paramount importance in conferring the specific biological activities in these molecules. Literature is replete with wide variety of examples of nitrogen containing rings present at face 'a' and 'c' of 1,4-benzodiazepine nucleus^{8,9} but its annelation through sulphur containing rings on the corresponding positions has been less known. The exploration of the chemistry of such

materials has been held back due to their inaccessibility by straightforward routes. The noteworthy biological properties exhibited by the sulphur containing bioactive materials suggested that compounds containing sulphur as a substituent or incorporated in a ring of 1,4-benzodiazepine nucleus were worthy of investigation¹⁰.

In continuation of our interest on the biologically active annelated 1,4-benzodiazepines, we reported¹¹ in an earlier article the synthesis of face-*c* annelated pyrrolidino- and thiazolidino-[1,4]-benzodiazepines from isatoic anhydride. In this communication we wish to report the synthesis of N_1 -(2-nitrophenyl sulphenyl substituted) pyrrolidino[2,1-*c*][1,4]-benzodiazepine (6), 4'-hydroxypyrrolidino[2,1-*c*][1,4]-benzodiazepine (7), thiazolidino[3,2-*c*][1,4]-benzodiazepine (8) and thiazolidino[4,3-*c*][1,4]-benzodiazepine (9) from isatoic anhydride. Compounds 6-9 contain a nitro group at 2'-position in N_1 -phenyl sulphenyl substituent which is capable of being amenable further to generate the corresponding thiazepine and thiazine ring annelated products 11 and 12 respectively (Fig. 1) on their reaction with triethyl phosphite¹² and by the Pschorr reaction on the corresponding amine¹³. Explorations pertaining to the accessibility of 11 and 12 using this strategy are under study.

Note

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

The reaction of isatoic anhydride with L-proline provides a very facile one pot synthetic entry to the pyrrolo[2,1-c][1,4]-benzodiazepine nucleus¹⁴. This reaction has been reported¹⁵ to take place through the formation of 10 (SR = H) from isatoic anhydride. This procedure has been employed in the present work in the synthesis of 6, 7, 8 and 9 from the reaction of 1 with 2, 3, 4

and 5 respectively (Scheme 1). The 1-(2'-nitrophenyl sulphenyl)-isatoic anhydride (1) required in the synthesis was obtained from the reaction of isatoic anhydride with 2-nitro phenyl sulphenyl chloride, following the procedure reported by Kricheldorf¹⁶. Although we have not attempted to establish the mechanistic details of the reaction of 1 with 2, 3, 4 and 5, but based on the earlier reports¹⁵ on the reaction of isatoic anhydride with bidentate polarophiles, we suggest that the reaction of N-substituted isatoic anhydride (1) too, proceeds through the formation of an imino ketene species (10) (Scheme 2). The structures of compounds 6~9 were established on the basis of elemental (N and S) and spectral (IR, ¹H NMR, MS) analysis (Tables 2 and 3). The spectral characteristics of the compounds 6-9 (Table 3) were found to be consistent to structures assigned to them in Fig. 2. The conditions of the reactions which gave better yield of the products are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Yield of compounds 6-9 obtained from the reaction of N-substituted isatoic anhydride (1) with 2-5, under conventional and MW conditions

Compd.	Reaction temp. (°C)			Time (min)			Yield (%)			M.p (°C)
	Convnt.	MW	MW	Convnt.	MW	MW	Convnt.	MW	MW	
		solvent	solid		solvent	solid		solvent	solid	
		phase	phase		phase	phase		phase	phase	
6	Reflux	120	130	360	10	8	54	65	76	235-237
7	Reflux	120	140	600	12	10	56	66	73	259-261
8	Reflux	120	120	480	12	10	53	64	72	210-212
9	Reflux	120	130	480	10	8	54	64	73	218-220

Table 2. Elemental analytical data of compounds 6-9

Compd.	Molecular formula	Molecular wt.	Elemental analysis (%) :	
			Calcd. (Found)	
			N	S
6	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	369.39	11.38 (10.96)	8.68 (8.10)
7	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅ S	385.39	10.90 (10.62)	8.32 (7.98)
8	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	387.43	10.85 (10.40)	16.55 (16.25)
9	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	387.43	10.85 (10.40)	16.55 (16.25)

The most diagnostic evidence for the formation of 8 (M⁺ = 387, 78%) from 1 was provided by its mass spectrum which showed the base peak I at m/z = 341 (100%), II 233 (86%), III 153 (18%), IV 122 (35%), V 75 (14%). The most probable pathway for the formation of fragments I~V from 8 is shown in Scheme 3. Mass spectral data of all the compounds 6-9 are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Spectral characteristics of compounds 6-9

Compd.	IR (cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (δ ppm)	MS
	KBr	CDCl ₃ + DMSO-d ₆	m/z (%)
6	1432 (C-N), 1522, 1345 (NO ₂), 1705, 1710 (two C=O), 1600-1575 (C=C ArH), 900 (S-N), 691 (C-S)	1.54-2.05 (4H, m, H _b and H _c), 3.36-4.30 (3H, m, H _a and H _d), 7.37-8.10 (8H, m, ArH)	369 (M ⁺ , 78), 323 (M ⁺ -46, 100), 215 (86), 153 (18), 122 (35), 75 (14)
7	1440 (C-N), 1530, 1350 (NO ₂), 1735, 1740 (two C=O), 1590-1570 (C=C ArH), 920 (S-N), 692 (C-S), 3420 (C ₃ -OH)	2.19 (1H, ddd, J 12.6, 9.5 and 4.2 Hz, H _b), 2.85 (1H, ddd, J 14, 8.0 and 4.2 Hz, H _b), 3.63 (1H, dd, J 13 and 4.0 Hz, H _d), 3.88 (1H, dd, J 13 and 4.0 Hz, H _d), 4.23 (1H, dd, J 14 and 12.6 Hz, H _a), 4.53 (1H, m, H _c), 4.74 (1H, d, J 4 Hz, H _c), 7.37-8.10 (8H, m, ArH)	385 (M ⁺ , 78), 339 (M ⁺ -46, 100), 231 (86), 153 (18), 122 (35), 75 (14)
8	1430 (C-N), 1520, 1340 (NO ₂), 1710, 1715 (two C=O), 1610-1580 (C=C ArH), 710 (C-S-C), 900 (S-N), 694 (C-S)	2.69-2.79 (2H, m, H _c and H _c), 3.52-3.62 (2H, m, H _d and H _d), 5.58 (1H, s, H _a), 7.37-8.10 (8H, m, ArH)	387 (M ⁺ , 78), 341 (M ⁺ -46, 100), 233 (86), 153 (18), 122 (35), 75 (14)
9	1430 (C-N), 1525, 1342 (NO ₂), 1712, 1715 (two C=O), 1615-1575 (C=C ArH), 712 (C-S-C), 900 (S-N), 694 (C-S)	2.96 (1H, dd, J 9.0 and 3.0 Hz, H _b), 3.21 (1H, dd, J 14 and 4.0 Hz, H _b), 4.30-4.40 (2H, m, H _d and H _d), 4.81 (1H, dd, J 14 and 9.0 Hz, H _a), 7.37-8.10 (8H, m, ArH)	387 (M ⁺ , 78), 341 (M ⁺ -46, 100), 233 (86), 153 (18), 122 (35), 75 (14)

Fig. 2

Experimental

All the melting points are taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The purity of all the compounds were checked by TLC using the solvent systems (benzene : methanol, 9 : 1 v/v) and silica gel G as adsorbent. IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR-8400 infra red spectrometer using KBr and ^1H NMR on Bruker AC 300 F in $\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO}-d_6$ (with chemical shifts expressed in δ , ppm) and mass spectra on a Jeol-JMS-D-300 mass spectrometer.

General method for the preparation of 1 :

A mixture of isatoic anhydride (0.815 g, 5 mmol) and *o*-nitrobenzene sulphenylchloride (0.948 g, 5 mmol) was refluxed for 6 h in 15 ml THF on a water bath. The mixture was poured in ice-cold water and then filtered and dried. Recrystallisation of the product from chloroform gave 1 (1.17 g) yield 74%, m.p. 229–230 °C, (231–233 °C)¹⁶.

Scheme 3. Mass spectral fragmentation of N_1 -(2-nitrophenyl sulphenyl substituted) thiazolidino[3,2-*c*][1,4]-benzodiazepine (**8**).

General method for the preparation of 8-11 :

(A) Conventional method :

A mixture of **1** (0.316 g, 1 mmol) and L-proline (**2**) (0.115 g, 1 mmol) was refluxed for 6 h in 20 ml glacial acetic acid. The resulting product was filtered, washed with ice cold water and dried. Recrystallization of the product from ethyl acetate gave **6** (0.20 g), yield 54%, m.p. 235–237 °C.

(B) Solution phase microwave assisted method :

A solution of **1** (0.316 g, 1 mmol) and L-proline (**2**) (0.115 g, 1 mmol) in glacial acetic acid was taken in a 100 ml borosil conical flask fitted with a funnel as a loose top. The reaction mixture was irradiated in a microwave at 110 °C for 10 min with short interval of 30 s to avoid the excessive evaporation of solvent. The mixture was cooled and diluted with ice cold water and dried to give **6** (0.24 g), yield 65%, m.p. 235–237 °C.

(C) Solid phase microwave assisted method :

In a typical run, a slurry of (**1**) (0.316 g, 1 mmol) and L-proline (**2**) (0.115 g, 1 mmol) and acidic alumina (3.5 g) was prepared in glacial acetic acid (1.5 ml). The dried slurry was powdered and the free flowing powder was placed in a 100 ml borosil conical flask, in an alumina bath and irradiated at 130 °C. The completion of the reaction was checked by TLC. The organic product was extracted from the inorganic solid support with ethyl acetate (3 × 5 ml). Evaporation of ethyl acetate gave **6** (1.77 g), yield 76%, m.p. 235–237 °C.

Similarly compounds **7-9** were prepared from the reaction of **1** with **3-5** following the methods **A**, **B** and **C** given above (conditions of the reaction, yield and m.p. of the products **7-9** are shown in Table 1).

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References

- (a) J. W. H. Wathey, J. L. Stanton and N. P. Peet, "Azepines, Part II in The Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds", eds. A. Weissberger and E. C. Taylor, Wiley, New York, 1984,

- (A monograph with 1010 references); (b) J. T. Sharp, "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry", eds. A. R. Katritzky and C. W. Rees, Pergamon, Oxford, 1984, 7, 608.
- G. Mohiuddin, P. S. Reddy, K. Ahmed and C. V. Ratnam, *Heterocycles*, 1986, **24**, 3489 (review with 217 references).
- D. E. Thurston and D. R. Langley, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1986, **51**, 705.
- J. Balzarini, A. Karlsson, M. J. Perez, M. J. Camarasa and W. G. Tarpley, *Journal of Virology*, 1993, 5353.
- (a) J. R. Lokensgard, C. C. Chao, G. Gekker, S. Hu and P. K. Peterson, *Molecular Neurobiology*, 1998, **18**, 23; (b) B. D. Puodziunaite, R. Janciene, L. Kosychova and Z. Stumbreviciute, *Arkivoc*, 2000, 1(iv), 512.
- (a) L. Kosychova, L. Pleckaitiene, Z. Staniulyte, R. Janciene, A. Palaima and B. D. Puodziunaite, *Arkivoc*, 2006, (xiii), 158; (b) G. Heinisch, E. Huber, B. Matuszczak, A. Maurer and U. Prillinger, *Arch. Pharm. (Weinheim)*, 1997, **330**, 29; (c) R. Pauwels, K. Andriesk, Z. Debyser, J. Kuklam and P. P. Janssen, *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 1994, **38**, 2863.
- R. Agarwal, PhD Thesis, Banasthali University, Banasthali, 1996.
- B. A. Roberte, K. Andries, J. Desayter, D. Schols, J. Kukla, H. Berslin, A. Raemaekers, J. V. Gleder, E. Declerq and P. Janseen, *Nature*, 1990, **343**, 470.
- B. A. Roberte, E. J. Valentine, H. M. Chu, T. Steve and Y. Kai, *Eur. Pat.*, 1991, 462, 522; *US. Pat.* 1990, 539, 500, (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1992, **116**, 128978f).
- A. Schmidt, G. Shilabin and M. Nieger, *Heterocycles*, 2004, **63**, 2851.
- S. Nain, M. Arya, V. Gupta, R. Sirohi and D. Kishore, *Int. J. Chem. Sci.*, 2008 (in Press).
- (a) A. R. Katritzky, Y. J. Xu and H. Y. He, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 2002, 592; (b) H. J. Reich and J. H. Rigby, "Handbook of Reagents for Organic Synthesis : Acidic and Basic Reagents", John Wiley and Sons, 1999, 417.
- F. W. Wassmundt and W. F. Kiesman, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1995, **60**, 196.
- Ahmed Kamal, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1991, **56**, 2237.
- G. Mohiuddin, P. S. N. Reddy, (Late) K. Ahmed and C. V. Ratnam, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1985, **24**, 905.
- V. H. R. Kricheldorf, *Angew. Chem.*, 1973, **2**, 85.